

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP4 – Predictive algorithms for early risk and disease detection, and decision support toolkit for precision prevention therapies

D4.1 Development of predictive algorithms

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset – Sweden (**The Coordinator**)
KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society – Sweden
FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute – Sweden
UGOT: Goteborgs Universitet – Sweden
ULUND: Lunds Universitet – Sweden
UEF: Itä-Suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland – Finland
AUMC: Stichting Amsterdam UMC – The Netherlands
UM: Universiteit Maastricht – The Netherlands
BBRC: Fundació Barcelonaβeta Brain Research Center – Spain
SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L – Spain
AE: Alzheimer Europe – Luxembourg
ADI: Alzheimer’s Disease International – United States
UNIPG: Università Degli Studi di Perugia – Italy
GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)
COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy – Finland
Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV – Belgium
SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development – France
C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States
neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH – Germany
CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom
DAVOS: Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative – United States
VGR: VÄSTRA GÖTALANDSREGIONEN – Sweden
ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom
ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine – United Kingdom
NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
SUS: SANOFI US Services Inc – United States
SADG: SANOFI-AVENTIS Deutschland GMBH – Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

WP4 focuses on developing and validating predictive algorithms and is connecting prediction and prevention via optimized use of data from existing observational cohorts and randomized controlled dementia prevention trials from several European countries, as well as new real-world testing of AD-related blood-based biomarkers and digital cognitive assessments. This deliverable provides a description of the work conducted in Task 4.1 Developing predictive algorithms for at-risk/early AD stages based on existing cohorts.

Mapping of relevant existing cohorts was conducted, and an additional PubMed search was done for new cohort identification to further increase generalizability of the findings. We considered a broad range of potential predictors, e.g. blood-based and other fluid biomarkers, digital biomarkers, neuroimaging, genetics, lifestyle factors. Data analysis methods included both traditional statistics and machine learning methods. In addition to the development of new algorithms/models, consideration was also given to testing existing highly relevant algorithms (e.g. dementia risk scores; cardiovascular or diabetes risk scores with factors relevant to dementia risk) to cover current knowledge gaps (e.g. testing in biomarker-positive populations, prediction of brain pathology).

Next steps will include (i) refinement of algorithms/models including also new data that will be collected during real-world testing of AD-related blood-based biomarkers and digital cognitive assessments, (ii) testing algorithms/models from observational cohorts in existing interventional RCTs, and (iii) developing a decision support toolkit to inform early precision preventive therapies.

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1. INTRODUCTION

WP4 focuses on developing and validating predictive algorithms and is connecting prediction and prevention via optimized use of data from existing observational cohorts and randomized controlled dementia prevention trials from several European countries, as well as data from new real-world testing of AD-related blood-based biomarkers (BBMs, WP3) and digital cognitive assessments (DCAs, WP2). The main WP4 objectives are to:

- 1) Develop and validate accurate predictive algorithms for early detection of people at risk or in early AD stages;
- 2) Develop predictive algorithms to identify risk/disease groups who are most likely to benefit from different dementia preventive therapies (non-pharmacological and/or pharmacological);
- 3) Develop a decision support toolkit to inform decision-making in early precision preventive therapies; and
- 4) Better understand AD mechanisms and factors affecting disease progression and preventive therapy effects.

An overview of the WP4 tasks and workflow is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of WP4.

This deliverable provides a description of the work conducted in *Task 4.1 Developing predictive algorithms for at-risk/early AD stages based on existing cohorts*. It also summarises alignment and collaborations with other relevant AD-RIDDLE WPs, and next steps.

2. METHODS

2.1 Definition of predictive algorithms/models

A broad definition of “predictive algorithm/model” was considered, covering (i) single- and multi-predictor modelling; (ii) prognostic and/or diagnostic models for future neuropathology, cognitive decline and/or dementia; and (iii) individual cohort or joint cross-cohort analyses as appropriate (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. General examples of considered algorithms / models

Data analysis methods included both traditional statistical methods (e.g. linear, logistic, Cox or competing risk regression) and machine learning (e.g. Disease State Index provided by Combinostics, decision trees, PCA, SEM) as appropriate for the relevant datasets.

2.2 Mapping of existing cohorts in collaboration with WP6

Mapping of relevant existing observational cohorts was conducted in collaboration with WP6, and also with the EU IMI European Platform for Neurodegenerative Diseases (EPND) project. Some of the Task 4.1 work also used data from existing FINGER-based randomized controlled trials (RCTs), where a non-randomised approach to data analysis was determined to be suitable (e.g. baseline-only or overall population analyses adjusting for group allocation). Mapping of existing RCT data was done in collaboration with WP6, and also the EU JPND-funded EU-FINGERS and Multi-MeMo projects. Non-randomised RCT data analysis was aligned with existing protocols in the World-Wide FINGERS network. Mapping of potential predictors covered e.g. blood-based and other fluid biomarkers, digital biomarkers, neuroimaging, genetics, lifestyle factors.

Several meetings were organised to plan the work and ensure harmonisation across tasks T4.1 and T4.3, WP6 and EPND contact points, e.g. WP4 co-leads meeting on 6th May 2024, meetings with WP6 and individual partners including cohort/RCT leads to discuss cohort-specific aspects, industry partners (e.g. exploratory blood-based biomarkers in the new real-world study and existing cohorts), and two WP4-wide meetings on 3rd February 2025 and 3rd April 2025.

2.3 New cohort identification

We aim to combine data from relevant AD-RIDDLE cohorts and the Amyloid Biomarker Study (ABS) with the goal of using this data for calculating prevalence estimates and developing prediction models (Table 1). The ABS is a global data pooling initiative which includes PET and CSF amyloid and tau data.

Table 1. Observational cohorts considered for AD-RIDDLE

Observational cohort	N
GEDOC	13000

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Bio-FINDER	1200
CHARIOT Pro	1136
Kuopio research cohort	200
ALFA+ cohort	420
Beta-AARC	200
GERICO	1500
Amsterdam (ADC, EMIF, cantate)	2000
EPND	350
Netherlands Consortium Dementia cohorts	2000
Amyloid biomarker study group (ABS)	7384
Other cohorts (143 identified)	

We have sought to expand the number of cohorts in the ABS by means of a PubMed search. The search term “((Alzheimer's disease) OR (Alzheimer) OR (AD)) AND ((plasma) OR (blood) OR (blood-based)) AND ((phosphorylated tau 217) OR (ptau217) OR (p-tau217) OR (ptau 217) OR (p-tau 217))” was entered into PubMed. This search identified 305 articles. First, all the duplicates (n = 17), review articles (n = 36), and corrections, replies and commentaries (n = 9) were removed. 2 of the remaining 243 articles were removed due to not being available in English. Second, 241 articles were screened for eligibility. Of these, 38 were excluded; 7 because they used animal or in-vitro models, 2 because they focused on a genetic form of AD, 17 because they did not focus on AD at all, and 12 because they had no plasma p-tau data available. All this resulted in 203 articles identified for inclusion (Figure 3). These 203 contained 143 unique cohorts which will be approached to ask for their plasma p-tau data. The collected data will then be used to determine the prevalence of plasma p-tau217 across the continuum of AD (normal cognition, NC / subjective cognitive decline, SCD / Mild Cognitive Impairment, MCI), dependent on age, APOE e4 carrier status, sex, education level, and comorbidities. In addition, the difference in prevalence of p-tau217 in and between different ethnic groups will be determined. Furthermore, data from relevant AD-RIDDLE cohorts will also be included in the analysis (Manuscript in preparation).

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Figure 3. Results from PubMed search

2.4 Alignment with WP7

Alignment points were established with WP7 as follows:

- *T7.3 (Health Technology Assessment, HTA)*: discussing how the HTA Standing Forum can help with better understanding of current evidence requirements and adoption pathways across different HTA agencies for clinical prediction models. A framework to gather information regarding the prediction models developed/tested as part of the project was agreed on to help WP7 map prediction algorithms/models against the methodology recommendations identified in the review of HTA agency methodology guidelines
- *T7.2 (Health economics)*: discussing potential use of prediction models/algorithms and related WP4 findings for health economics modelling

2.5 Testing existing algorithms

In addition to development of new algorithms, consideration was also given to testing existing algorithms with high relevance for both Task 4.1 and the FINGER-based intervention models in Task 4.3 to cover current knowledge gaps (e.g. testing in biomarker-positive populations, prediction of brain pathology). Selection of relevant existing risk scores was based on a literature review and the available predictors identified during cohort mapping. Dementia shares several risk factors with other common chronic noncommunicable

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diseases such as diabetes, stroke and cardiovascular diseases, and this needs to be taken into account in the decision support toolkit for early preventive therapies to be developed in Task 4.4. Thus, we included not only dementia risk scores, but also existing risk scores originally developed for predicting diabetes, stroke and cardiovascular diseases. In addition to risk scores based on modifiable factors, polygenic scores for AD and coronary artery disease were also considered (Table 2).

Table 2. Brief overview of relevant existing risk scores selected for further testing

Risk Score	Condition developed for	Target population	Development Method	Country developed in	Predictor Type
CAIDE	Dementia	Mid-Life	Population-based cohort study	Finland	Integer (0-15, -APOE; 0/18 +APOE) associated to 20-year estimates (%)
LIBRA	Dementia	18+	Umbrella review and Delphi consensus study	Multi-country	Integer (-5.9 - +12.7)
ANUADRI	Alzheimer's Disease	Adults	Systematic review	Multi-country	Integer (-17 - +76)
WHICAP	Alzheimer's Disease	65+	Community based cohort study	US	Integer (0-70)
Hisayama	Dementia	65+	Population-based cohort study	Japan	Integer 0-18 associated to 10-year risk estimates (%)
BDSI	Dementia	65+	Population-based cohort studies	US	Integer (Age in years + additional points range 0 to 42)
DRS	Dementia	60+ with diabetes	Large primary-care population study	UK	Weighted score each factor continuous or dichotomous multiplied by a coefficient
UKBDRS	Dementia	50+	UK Biobank and Whitehall II cohort studies	UK	Weighted score each factor continuous or dichotomous multiplied by a coefficient
SCORE	CVD Mortality (CHD+Stroke)	40-65	MA of multiple population-based cohort studies	Europe	10-year risk estimates (%)
SCORE-OP	CVD ^a Mortality	65+	MA of multiple population-based cohort studies	Europe	10-year risk estimates (%)
FINRISK	CVD ^a Morbidity	30-74	Population-based cohort study	Finland	10-year risk estimates (%)
FHRS	CVD ^b	30+	Population-based cohort study	US	10-year risk estimates (%)
GVRS	CVD ^c	40+	Population-based cohort study	US	Weighted score (each factor continuous or dichotomous multiplied by a coefficient)
LS7	CHD	N/A	Literature review and evidence from cohort studies	US	Integer (0 to 14, the higher the lower the risk)
QRisk	CVD ^d	35-74	Large primary-care population study	UK	10-year risk estimates (%)
FSRS	Stroke	30-74	Population-based cohort study	US	10-year risk estimates (%)

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QStroke	Stroke	25-84	Large primary-care population study	UK	10-year risk estimates (%)
FINDRISK	Diabetes	40-64	Population-based cohort study	Finland	Integer (0 to 20)
LSAS	Diabetes	40-75	Population-based cohort study	UK	Integer (0 to 47)
AD-GRS	Dementia	Developed in adults, validated in 50+	GWAS meta-analysis on multiple consortia datasets and validation on prospective, population-based cohorts and MCI memory clinics	Europe	Continuous numerical with decimals notations; >0
CAD-GRS	Coronary artery disease	Developed in adults (mostly European ancestry), validated in UKBB	GWAS meta-analysis on multiple datasets, validation in UKBB	Europe	Continuous numerical with decimals notations; >0

AD-GRS: Alzheimer disease genetic risk score; ANU-ADRI: Australian National University Alzheimer's Disease Risk Index; BDSI: Brief Dementia Screening Indicator; CAD-GRS: coronary artery disease genetic risk score; CAIDE: Cardiovascular Risk Factors, Aging, and Incidence of Dementia; CHD: Coronary Heart Disease; CVD: Cardiovascular Disease; DRS: Dementia Risk Score; FINDRISK: Finnish Diabetes Risk Score; FINRISK: Finnish Cardiovascular Risk Score; FHRS: Framingham Heart Risk Score; FSRS: Framingham Stroke Risk Score; GVRS: Global Vascular Risk Score; LIBRA: Lifestyle for Brain Health; LS7: Life Simple7; LSAS: Leicester Self-Assessment Risk Score; MA: Meta-Analysis; SCORE: Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation; SCORE-OP: Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation-Older People; UKBDRS: UK Biobank Dementia Risk Score; WHICAP: Washington Heights-Inwood Columbia Aging Project.

- Combined coronary heart disease and stroke.*
- Defined as specific atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease events, i.e., coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, peripheral vascular disease, and heart failure.*
- MI, stroke, or vascular death.*
- Defined as a composite outcome of coronary heart disease, ischaemic stroke, or transient ischaemic attack*

3 RESULTS

3.1 Literature review on BBMs and their performance as predictors of AD

3.1.1 Predictors of amyloid positivity

From the PubMed search mentioned above, data is being extracted to be used to develop a prediction model that will predict a person's amyloid status (positive or negative). Thus far, we have seen that, in the 20 articles we investigated, plasma p-tau217 seemed to be the best blood-based biomarker for predicting amyloid status. Moreover, a slight increase in prediction accuracy was seen when adding the following factors to the model with plasma p-tau217 alone: age, APOE e4 carrier status, polygenic risk score, cognitive measures/digital markers, and lifestyle factors.

Regarding disease staging, we found that the accuracy of predicting amyloid pathology by plasma p-tau217 was lower in cognitively normal individuals than in individuals with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or patients with dementia. (Manuscript in preparation)

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3.1.2 Predictors of cognitive decline

For looking at predictors of cognitive decline, 10 cohorts were selected. Here we concluded from the literature that plasma p-tau217 was the best predictor for future cognitive decline. While plasma p-tau217 alone was a good predictor, adding other blood-based biomarkers to the model, such as p-tau181, did improve the prediction accuracy. (Manuscript in preparation)

3.2 New prediction modelling

3.2.1 AD-related BBMs and cognitive decline

AD-related BBM data on A β 42/40 ratio, p-tau181, NfL and GFAP were available in 8 cohorts of the Netherlands Consortium of Dementia Cohorts including 2554 samples. The association between each of these BBM and cognitive decline over time across the domains of memory (immediate and delayed recall), language and global cognition was examined separately in each cohort and is being combined with meta-analytic techniques. To allow for federated analyses across those 8 cohorts, NCDC makes use of the privacy-by-design Personal Health Train (PHT) infrastructure. The core strength of the PHT infrastructure is that data does not leave the host institution, thereby ensuring optimal data privacy and control of data. The PHT infrastructure consists of “stations” at each institute, where harmonized data is uploaded to a local server and “tracks” through which analytical algorithms and results of locally run analyses (“trains”) can be exchanged. To establish the PHT infrastructure, the necessary software was installed at each institute and the minimal dataset variables were harmonized to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model (CDM) and uploaded to the PHT environment.

We are using linear mixed models corrected for age, sex and education to examine the associations between BBM and cognitive decline. Preliminary analyses show that, overall, NfL is most strongly associated to memory decline over time. In women, NfL was associated with decline on memory and language domains. In men, GFAP was associated with decline on memory and language domains. In APOE-e4 carriers, BBM did not significantly predict cognitive decline while in APOE-e4 noncarriers, NfL and GFAP were associated with decline on memory and language domains. Analyses are ongoing (Manuscript in preparation).

3.2.2 BBM profiling in FINGER-based RCTs cohorts (non-randomised approach)

AD-related BBM data were available from 3197 samples from FINGER participants collected at 3 timepoints over 11 years, analysed using the Nucleic Acid Linked Immuno-Sandwich Assay (NULISA) central nervous system panel (120 biomarkers) and the p-tau217 fully automated Lumipulse immunoassay. Initial analyses focused on core AD BBMs (p-tau217, A β 42/40, NfL, GFAP) to characterize the baseline status and longitudinal changes in a population at risk of dementia but without substantial impairment at baseline. Preliminary results show that about 20% of the FINGER participants were initially in the intermediate or pathological p-tau217 range. Stratifying participants by APOE4 genotype showed distinct trajectories over the 11-year follow-up period, with APOE4 carriers having a significant increase in levels of several of the core AD BBMs. While the APOE4 carrier group had a mean p-tau217 level in the normal range at baseline, the mean p-tau217 reached pathological level at the 11-years follow-up. Analyses are ongoing with all available

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120 BBMs to investigate biomarker profiles associated to different cognitive trajectories in people at risk of dementia.

Similar analyses with the core AD BBMs are ongoing in the FINGER-NL trial and are planned in the MET-FINGER trial.

Other BBMs included e.g. glucose-related and metabolic markers in FINGER participants. We conducted the first comprehensive longitudinal study examining the association between a broad range of continuous glycaemia-related markers with both cognitive function and neuroimaging measures over two years. In older people at-risk for dementia without previously diagnosed diabetes, only OGTT markers were predictive of changes across multiple cognitive domains and neuroimaging outcomes. OGTT measures may thus be more sensitive in detecting subtle glucose metabolism abnormalities associated with unfavourable cognitive changes over time. As HbA1c has lower sensitivity for detecting early dysglycaemia compared with OGTT, these markers may show conflicting associations with cognition and neuroimaging measures in people without dementia and previously diagnosed diabetes. These findings emphasise the importance of selecting more accurate glucose-related markers when investigating the early stages of glucose metabolism abnormalities in relation to subtle cognitive impairment and its structural brain correlates. Accurate glucose-related markers could also contribute to a more precise selection of individuals at-risk for dementia who may benefit most from preventive interventions including dysglycaemia monitoring and management (Lorenzo T et al, accepted for publication in Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews).

We are also conducting complex metabolomics analysis to investigate metabolic profiles related to cognitive trajectories. Untargeted 2-year metabolomics were analysed with data in 1089 participants. LC-MS data included 10 825 metabolomic features (6000 annotated); 1H NMR was used to quantify 40 small molecules and 112 lipoprotein fractions. A manuscript is currently in preparation including associations between plasma metabolite patterns and 2-year cognitive changes. Analyses are planned for associations between plasma metabolite and core AD BBMs.

3.2.3 Predicting positive biomarker status in real-world memory clinic populations

We built prediction models using the Disease State Index tool provided by Combinostics to find the optimal set of tests to predict positive status for different CSF or MRI biomarkers related to AD. Initially we built models for 443 participants without dementia from the Karolinska University Hospital Solna memory clinic and compared them with 1763 participants from the MemClin cohort (including other memory clinics in the Stockholm region in Sweden). We tested a number of different biomarkers related to ATN pathology. Amyloid pathology (A) was tested with CSF A β 42 and the ratio of A β 42/40, tau pathology (T) with CSF pTau and neurodegeneration (N) with CSF total tau, NfI and MTA. Additionally, we tested white matter changes with Fazekas scale and an AD profile with the combination of A β and tau positivity. We either built Gaussian models to find optimal biomarker cut-offs or used pre-established cut-offs as appropriate. Clinical variables for the prediction models included demographics, such as age and education, comorbidities and medications for cardiovascular diseases, diabetes or depression, blood pressure and cholesterol measurements, various cognitive or neuropsychological tests, MRI analysis with both manual and automatic MTA and Fazekas, automated GCA and extensive volumetry, and the APOE genotype. Additionally, we tested AD plasma

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biomarkers as predictors for the CSF and MRI biomarkers. We selected different combinations of clinical variables to predict biomarker positivity with the DSI using 10-fold cross-validation to find out optimal sets of variables for the predictions. Models were compared using AUC values. A manuscript is in preparation.

In real-life memory clinic data (Karolinska Solna), we have additionally investigated optimal combinations of available core AD BBMs to identify individuals potentially eligible for new amyloid-targeted AD drugs using Gaussian mixed modelling and decision tree modelling. The reference standard for AD pathology was based on F18-amyloid PET scans and CSF assays. A manuscript is in preparation.

3.3 Testing of existing dementia, diabetes and cardiovascular risk scores in relation to BBMs and other AD biomarkers

While a higher CAIDE dementia risk score may reflect the potential for lifestyle-based dementia risk reduction in individuals without substantial impairment, its associations with dementia risk are less clear in populations with specific cognitive and neuropathological profiles. Using ADNI data, we investigated to what extent the CAIDE score was related to clinical progression of cognitive impairment in the presence or absence of A β and p-tau pathology. Analysing cognitively unimpaired and MCI individuals separately, we found that the association of CAIDE score with progression varied depending on the presence or absence of AD pathological changes. Thus, even after the onset of AD pathology, addressing modifiable risk factors remains critical to reducing the risk of dementia (Huszar et al, Alzheimer’s Research and Therapy 2024, DOI: 10.1186/s13195-024-01602-9).

We analysed the associations of CAIDE and LIBRA dementia risk scores with a panel of 12 glucose and lipid related metabolic blood biomarkers in the FINGER cohort. The panel included adiponectin, adipsin, c-peptide, ghrelin, gastric inhibitor polypeptide (GIP), glucagon-like-peptide (GLP-1), glucagon, insulin, leptin, plasminogen activator in plasma (PAI-1), resistin, and visfatin, and was measured using Bio-Plex-200. Higher CAIDE score was associated with unfavourable profiles of several metabolic markers (manuscript in preparation).

Established cardiovascular risk scores (FINRISK 2.0, Framingham, SCORE-OP, and LS7) were investigated for the first time head-to-head in the FINGER cohort in relation to cognition and neuroimaging. Three of the four risk scores showed consistent associations with 2-year cognitive trajectories and either FDG-PET or MRI measures. A manuscript is currently in preparation. FINRISK 2.0 score, which is commonly used in Finland for cardiovascular risk detection and targeting cardiovascular disease prevention measures, was also investigated for the first time in relation to dementia incidence over 40 years in a population-based cohort. Higher FINRISK score was associated with an increased risk of developing dementia after adjusting for socioeconomic factors and accounting for death as a competing risk. Interaction analysis showed that the FINRISK score may perform better in predicting dementia in participants with higher education and income level (Master thesis; manuscript in preparation).

We investigated whether two previously validated comprehensive polygenic risk scores for AD (AD-GRS) and coronary artery disease (CAD-GRS) were related to cognition in the FINGER cohort. The AD-GRS showed associations with some of the cognitive measures, but the association pattern was less evident than for

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APOE4 allele. The CAD-GRS did not seem to be related to cognition. Further analyses considering impact on intervention effects are ongoing (manuscript in preparation).

Analyses are ongoing to assess risk scores listed in Table 2 in relation to core AD BBMs in the FINGER cohort.

3.4 Prediction modelling with real-world MRI data

We have been developing and testing a methodological framework for real-world evidence AD studies using brain MRIs routinely collected during 20 years in the regional PACS of a large public healthcare provider (North Savo Wellbeing services area in Eastern Finland). AD-relevant biomarkers derived from routine brain MRI scans were compared in a real-world population-based MRI cohort versus an established research cohort reference with a strict imaging protocol (ADNI). The extracted biomarkers were shown to be suitable for generating real-world evidence (RWE) in AD research, and a methodological framework was provided for future RWE AD studies using routinely collected MRIs (Sund et al, accepted for publication in *Alzheimer's and Dementia*, doi: 10.1101/2025.02.13.25322207).

Analyses are ongoing to test several risk scores listed in Table 2 in relation to longitudinal changes in brain MRI markers and cognition.

4 DISCUSSION

The increasing availability of core AD BBMs in existing cohorts opens a new array of potential cohorts to be included for AD biomarker research. We have started the initiative of combined analysis of these cohorts. This will lead to increased generalizability of the findings. Our literature review on AD-related BBMs showed that plasma p-tau217 is the BBM with the best predictive performance for amyloid positivity. This further supports the work being done in WP3, including the decision to focus the primary and secondary outcomes of the real-world BBM testing study on p-tau217 based markers.

WP4 work will continue in Task 4.2 with close alignment with both WP3 and WP2 in planning and conducting a broad range of exploratory analyses focused on predictive algorithms/models including new data from the real-world testing of BBMs and digital cognitive assessments.

Prediction algorithms/models developed based on existing observational cohorts in Task 4.1 are also being assessed for suitability of testing in existing FINGER-based RCTs (Task 4.3). Examples of potential real-life scenarios to be modelled using existing RCT data include:

- Targeted screening - for selecting at-risk individuals for lifestyle-based interventions
- Targeted interventions - identifying which at-risk groups benefit most from various FINGER-based interventions
- Cost-benefit estimations – using prediction algorithms/models as RCT outcomes and assessing the intervention-related risk modification; risk reduction estimates could be provided to WP7 for further health economic modelling.

Task 4.1 findings on other biomarkers beyond the core AD BBMs and addressing current knowledge gaps in how existing risk scores (originally developed to predict dementia, cardio/cerebrovascular conditions or

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diabetes) relate to cognitive decline and/or neuropathology provide information with high relevance for the development of the decision support toolkit in Task 4.4. Consideration of multifactorial vascular and diabetes risk scores based on shared risk factors with dementia is also expected to facilitate integration of lifestyle-based dementia risk reduction strategies with existing programs for prevention of heart disease, stroke or diabetes.

5 CONCLUSION

Building on the work already done within this work package, we will continue analysing and expanding existing data with the goal of creating reliable and generalizable prediction algorithms/models. These models will be an essential part of the decision support toolkit.